

Collatz on Mersenne exponents

Adolf Cusmariu

Email: adolcus@gmail.com

Limited numerical experiments [1] showed that Collatz iteration will terminate fairly quickly on primes when started on primes; results on the 50 known (odd) Mersenne exponents [2] are presented below. Each table has the starters in boldface white-type in the first row, stops in boldface red in the second, and the number of passes in the third.

3	5	7	13	17	19	31	61	89	107
2	2	17	5	13	29	47	23	67	137
4	3	2	3	2	1	1	3	2	6
127	521	607	1279	2203	2281	3217	4253	4423	9689
191	587	911	2879	3719	3851	1019	2393	18899	1151
1	3	1	2	4	4	8	4	9	11
9941	11213	19937	21701	23209	44497	86243	110503	132049	216091
233	2663	16823	859	26111	18773	379	177007	37139	1557623
7	10	5	11	3	6	11	12	5	13
756839	859433	1257787	1398269	2976221	3021377	6972593	13466917	20996011	24036583
4310441	966863	27983	1769687	627797	3989	735391	2130509	4489273	60842603
7	3	15	6	7	27	8	9	27	5
25964951	30402457	32582657	37156667	42643801	43112609	57885161	74207281	77232917	82589933
4107737	2029121	61231	464983	150089	61384949	65120807	17609737	3620293	34842629
9	15	36	19	24	9	3	10	6	6

The image below charts these results; the top tier has the primes in dB (10log10) scale, with stops in red stars; the bottom tier shows iteration counts, unusually many in a few cases (boldface black in yellow-highlight above).

The largest Mersenne prime workable in OCTAVE reaches a prime after only three Collatz iterations:

$$2^{31} - 1 = 2147483647 \rightarrow 3221225471 \rightarrow 4831838207 \rightarrow 7247757311$$

References

- [1] A. Cusmariu, 'Collatz on more primes', <https://zenodo.org/records/10871130>
 [2] Wikipedia article on the Mersenne primes.